

FOODITY News

Stories on food, data and digital innovation

As we begin a new year, we're excited to share a gift from the FOODITY community with you

Over the past months, we've been busy turning 3 years of collaboration and innovation into practical, inspiring resources.

From a community-driven [Recipe Book](#) bringing together 28 contributors to an [Innovators Booklet](#) showcasing 20 data-driven food and nutrition solutions — both presented at our [final conference in Brussels](#), celebrated together with our sister project, DRG4FOOD.

These resources reflect what FOODITY is all about: **community, citizen empowerment, trust, and digital innovation for healthier, more sustainable food systems.**

Take a look at what we've been working on, and enjoy this gift.

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FOODITY resources you can use (and share!)

The FOODITY & DRG4FOOD Innovators Booklet

This booklet showcases the **20 funded projects supported through FOODITY & DRG4FOOD.**

It highlights how innovators across Europe are using AI, open data, privacy-by-design, and GDPR-aligned infrastructures to support personalised nutrition, improve food transparency and traceability, reduce food waste, and empower citizens to understand and control their data.

At the heart of every solution is a shared commitment to **personal data sovereignty**, ensuring **digital innovation truly serves people and the planet**.

Download the Innovators Booklet

The FOODITY Recipe Book

Bringing together **28 recipes** from **12 European countries**, this book features contributions from FOODITY partners and innovators, the DRG4FOOD team, members of the Data4Food cluster, and our collaborators.

More than a cookbook, it combines **food traditions** and **personal stories** with **reflections on data sovereignty, sustainability, and digital innovation**.

Whether you're looking for inspiration for your next meal or curious about how digital tools influence our eating habits and wellbeing, this book invites you to cook, think and live more mindfully.

Download the Recipe Book

If you try any of the recipes from our [#FOODITYRecipeBook](#), share them and tag us on social media!

**Where it all came together: the FOODITY &
DRG4FOOD Final Conference**

These resources were presented at our final conference, **“A Recipe for Trust: Food, Data and Our Choices”**, held on 22–23 October 2025 in Brussels, together with our sister project, DRG4FOOD.

Over two days, innovators, researchers, policymakers, and food & data professionals came together to learn about the solutions developed by our 20 funded pilots, participate in panel discussions and interactive workshops, and connect with peers across the ecosystem.

The conference also provided the stage for **ONCONOURISH**, a personalised nutrition support tool for people undergoing cancer treatment, to receive the **2nd FOODITY Star Award**.

[Read the full event recap](#) →

**Voices from the FOODITY & DRG4FOOD
community**

Our final event recap video features insights from:

- **FOODITY & DRG4FOOD coordinators**, reflecting on three years of collaboration
- **Innovators from both projects**: ONCONOURISH, Cacao-Tech, REDUCE, GENIE, SEBP and DISH

Through short interviews, they share what their solutions are about and how our support programmes have helped them.

[Watch the video](#) →

While FOODITY is coming to a close, **the community, technologies, and solutions we've built will continue to shape the future of food and nutrition.**

We're really proud of what we've achieved and grateful to everyone who contributed along the way.

Thank you to our innovators, partners, collaborators, and community members for your trust and commitment.

Let's keep cooking up a better future for food systems in 2026 and beyond!

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